

IMPLEMENTATION OF MODERN METHODS OF CALCULATING QUALITY INDICATORS

B.K. Asadov

UzAuto Motos JCS, Andijan, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *This paper explores modern methods for calculating quality indicators in production processes. Key quality metrics, including First Time Quality (FTQ), Parts Per Million (PPM), Rework and Scrap rates, and the Cost of Quality (CoQ), are discussed. These indicators enable organizations to assess production efficiency, identify areas for improvement, reduce costs, and enhance customer satisfaction. The author emphasizes the importance of accurate measurement and proactive quality management to achieve competitive advantages and operational excellence.*

В данной статье рассматриваются современные методы расчета показателей качества в производственных процессах. Описаны ключевые индикаторы качества, такие как First Time Quality (FTQ), Parts Per Million (PPM), Доработка и Списание, а также Стоимость качества (CoQ). Эти показатели помогают организациям измерять эффективность производства, выявлять области для улучшений, снижать затраты и повышать удовлетворенность клиентов. Автор подчеркивает важность точных измерений и проактивного управления качеством для достижения конкурентных преимуществ и операционного совершенства.

Keywords: *quality indicators, First Time Quality (FTQ), Parts Per Million (PPM), Rework, Scrap, Cost of Quality (CoQ), production efficiency, quality management, operational excellence.*

Introduction

Quality management is essential in today's competitive market environment. The pursuit of high-quality standards, sustained customer satisfaction, and efficient production processes are pivotal to business success. "Quality" encompasses more than just the end product; it includes all aspects of the production process, waste management, and cost efficiency. Quality indicators, therefore, are metrics used to measure the performance of processes and products against set standards. These indicators reveal inefficiencies, ensure compliance, and drive continuous improvement.

This paper explores the implementation of modern methods to calculate quality indicators, focusing on **First Time Quality (FTQ), Parts Per Million (PPM), Rework and Scrap rates**, and the **Cost of Quality (CoQ)**. Each of these indicators plays a vital role in assessing and managing quality within production environments. Through accurate measurement, companies can not only ensure product reliability and customer satisfaction but also optimize operational costs. Understanding how to calculate these quality metrics accurately is key to refining manufacturing processes and enhancing overall efficiency.

MAIN PART

1. First Time Quality (FTQ)

First Time Quality (FTQ) is a metric used to determine the percentage of products manufactured correctly on the first attempt without requiring rework or repair. This metric highlights the efficiency of a production line and measures how well a process conforms to quality specifications. The FTQ formula is:

$$FTQ = \frac{G}{T} \times 100\%$$

G – Number of good units produced on first attempt

T – Total Units Produced

A high FTQ rate indicates a streamlined process with fewer defects, reducing the need for corrective actions, which in turn decreases production costs. FTQ can be evaluated at various production stages to detect areas where improvement is necessary. Advanced tracking and software tools can assist in calculating FTQ in real-time, providing valuable insights for quick decision-making.

2. Parts Per Million (PPM)

Parts Per Million (PPM) is a quality metric that reflects the number of defective parts per million units produced. It is widely used in industries like automotive and electronics, where strict quality standards are crucial. PPM provides a way to track defect levels and benchmark quality against industry standards or competitor performance. PPM is calculated using the following formula:

$$PPM = \left(\frac{D}{T}\right) \times 1\,000\,000$$

D – Number of Defective Parts

T – Total Units Produced

A low PPM score demonstrates high-quality production, while a high PPM score signifies potential quality issues. Implementing methods like Statistical Process Control (SPC) and Six Sigma can help in reducing PPM by identifying and addressing root causes of defects. Statistical Process Control (SPC) is a powerful quality control method that uses statistical techniques to monitor, control, and improve production processes. SPC aims to ensure that a process operates at its full potential to produce products that meet quality standards consistently. By detecting and correcting variations in real time, SPC helps maintain a steady production process, reduce defects, and minimize waste.

3. Rework and Scrap

Rework and Scrap are two key quality indicators related to production waste. Rework refers to the process of correcting defective products, while Scrap pertains to materials that are entirely discarded. Both impact operational costs and indicate areas where production processes may need improvement.

- **Rework Rate:** Calculating the rework rate helps in understanding how many units need correction due to quality issues. This rate can be determined by dividing the number of reworked units by the total number of units produced.

$$\text{Rework Rate} = \left(\frac{R}{T}\right) \times 100\%$$

R – Number of reworked units

T – Total Units Produced

- Scrap Rate: The scrap rate reveals the proportion of materials that are discarded. Lowering the scrap rate not only conserves resources but also enhances sustainability efforts.

$$\text{Scrap Rate} = \left(\frac{S}{T} \right) \times 100\%$$

S – Number of scrapped units

T – Total Units Produced

By implementing preventive maintenance, quality control inspections, and root cause analysis, companies can decrease rework and scrap rates, optimizing resource usage.

4. Cost of Quality (CoQ)

The Cost of Quality (CoQ) is a comprehensive metric that calculates the total cost associated with ensuring good quality. It includes costs related to prevention, appraisal, and failure. The CoQ framework breaks down into four major categories:

- Prevention Costs: Expenses to prevent defects, including training, process control, and quality planning.
- Appraisal Costs: Costs associated with measuring and monitoring quality, such as inspections and testing.
- Internal Failure Costs: Costs related to defects identified before products reach customers, including rework and scrap.
- External Failure Costs: Expenses incurred after defective products reach customers, like warranty claims and recalls.

The total CoQ is often presented as a percentage of total sales or production costs. Reducing CoQ requires a holistic approach to quality management, leveraging metrics like FTQ, PPM, rework, and scrap rates to inform strategic decisions.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of modern methods for calculating quality indicators brings substantial benefits to businesses. By accurately measuring FTQ, PPM, Rework, Scrap, and CoQ, companies gain a clearer view of their production efficiency and quality standards. These calculations enable businesses to identify areas for improvement, leading to cost savings, enhanced customer satisfaction, and sustained market competitiveness. Moreover, these indicators allow for proactive quality management, reducing the likelihood of costly recalls and improving brand reputation.

Investing in robust quality measurement systems facilitates continuous improvement, ensuring companies can swiftly adapt to changing quality demands. The benefits of modern quality calculation methods extend beyond production floors, influencing customer loyalty, profitability, and overall business success. Through diligent quality management practices, businesses can achieve operational excellence and maintain their competitive edge.

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